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Research Article

**OCCURRENCE OF NEPHROLITHIASIS & MICROLITHIASIS
A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON
HAEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS IN TERTIARY CARE
HOSPITAL IN HYDERABAD**

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Abstract:

Objectives: The main objective of our study was a prospective observational study on haemodialysis patients.

Method: The study "A prospective observational study on Haemodialysis patients in a tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad" was carried out in the dialysis unit at Yashoda Hospital Malakpet, Hyderabad; from 6-months that was from December 2013 to May 2014 was collected from 350 bedded multi-disciplinary tertiary care hospital.

Result: A prospective observational study was conducted for six months (Dec-2013 to May-2014) in the Dialysis unit of Yashoda Hospital, a Tertiary care hospital, Hyderabad. A total of 50 Haemodialysis (D) patients were selected for the study according to the inclusion criteria.

Evaluation of Data: A total of 50 patients underwent haemodialysis, out of 3,100 IP (Inpatient) admissions during the study period. Out of 50 HD patients, 16 patients were new patients during the study period. The present study shows the Incidence for haemodialysis is 0.005 and the Prevalence for haemodialysis is 0.016.

Conclusion: In HYDERABAD region, there is a relatively high prevalence and incidence of renal failure. Hypertension and Diabetes mellitus are the leading causes for the kidney diseases. Weakness, nausea and vomiting are the prominent intra dialysis complications. HCV infections and psychiatric illness are the long term dialysis complications. So maintenance of hygienic conditions during dialysis and patients counselling is needed.

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INTRODUCTION:

The kidneys are a pair of vital organs that perform many functions to keep the blood clean and chemically balanced. The kidneys are bean-shaped organs, each about the size of a fist. They are located near the middle of the back, just below the rib cage, one on each side of the spine. The kidneys are sophisticated reprocessing machines. Kidneys process about 200 quarts of blood to sift out about 2 quarts of waste products and extra water per a day. The wastes and extra water become urine, which flows to the bladder through tubes called ureters. The bladder stores urine until releasing it through urination. In the nephron (left), tiny blood vessels intertwine with urine-collecting tubes. Each kidney contains about one million nephrons

FUNCTIONS OF KIDNEY:

The kidney participates in whole-body homeostasis, regulating acid-base balance, electrolyte concentrations, extracellular fluid volume, and regulation of blood pressure. The kidney accomplishes these homeostatic functions both independently and in concert with other organs, particularly those of the endocrine system. Various endocrine hormones coordinate these endocrine functions; these include renin, angiotensin II, aldosterone, antidiuretic hormone, and atrial natriuretic peptide, among others.

Many of the kidney's functions are accomplished by relatively simple mechanisms of filtration, reabsorption, and secretion, which take place in the nephron. Filtration, which takes place at the renal corpuscle, is the process by which cells and large proteins are filtered from the blood to make an ultra filtrate that eventually becomes urine. The kidney generates 180 liters of filtrate a day, while reabsorbing a large percentage, allowing for the generation of only approximately 2 liters of urine. Reabsorption is the

transport of molecules from this ultrafiltrate and into the blood. Secretion is the reverse process, in which molecules are transported in the opposite direction, from the blood into the urine.

1. Excretion of wastes: The kidneys excrete a variety of waste products produced by metabolism. These include the nitrogenous wastes called "urea", from protein catabolism, as well as uric acid, from nucleic acid metabolism. Formation of urine is also the function of the kidney. This requires several independent nephron characteristics to operate: a tight hair pin configuration of the tubules, water and ion permeability in the descending limb of the loop, water impermeability in the ascending loop and active ion transport out of most of the ascending loop. In addition, countercurrent exchange by the vessels carrying the blood supply to the nephron is essential for enabling this function. 2. Reabsorption of vital nutrients: Glucose at normal plasma levels is completely reabsorbed in the proximal tubule. The mechanism for this is the Na⁺/glucose co-transporter. A plasma level of 350 mg/dL will fully saturate the transporters and glucose will be lost in the urine. A plasma level of approximately 160mg/dL is sufficient to allow glucosuria which is an important clue to diagnose DM (Diabetes Mellitus). Amino acids are reabsorbed by sodium dependent transporters in the proximal tubule.

3. **Acid-base homeostasis:** Two organ systems, the kidneys and lungs, maintain acid-base homeostasis, which is the maintenance of pH around a relatively stable value. The lungs contribute the acid-base homeostasis by regulating carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentration. The kidneys have two very important roles in maintaining the acid-base balance: to reabsorb bicarbonate from urine, and to excrete hydrogen ions into urine.

Table-1.1: Description of renal reabsorption of vital nutrients²

Location of Reabsorption	Reabsorbed nutrient	Notes
Early proximal tubule	Glucose (100%), amino acids (100%), bicarbonate (90%), Na ⁺ (65%), Cl ⁻ , phosphate and H ₂ O (65%)	PTH will inhibit phosphate excretion. AT-II stimulates Na ⁺ , H ₂ O and HCO ₃ ³⁻ reabsorption.
Thin descending loop of Henle	H ₂ O	Reabsorbs via medullary hypertonicity and makes urine hypertonic.
Thick ascending loop of Henle	Na ⁺ (10-20%), K ⁺ , Cl ⁻ ; indirectly induces para cellular reabsorption of Mg ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	This region is impermeable to H ₂ O and the urine becomes less concentrated as it ascends.
Early distal convoluted tubule	Na ⁺ , Cl ⁻	PTH causes Ca ²⁺ reabsorption.
Collecting tubules	Na ⁺ (3-5%), H ₂ O	Aldosteroneregulates the reabsorption of Na ⁺ in exchangefor K ⁺ and H ⁺ . ADH inserts aquaporins on the luminal side.

Osmolality regulation: Any significant rise in plasma osmolality is detected by the hypothalamus, which communicates directly with the posterior pituitary gland. An increase in osmolality causes the gland to secrete antidiuretic hormone (ADH), resulting in water reabsorption by the kidney and an increase in urine concentration. The two factors work together to return the plasma osmolality to its normal levels. ADH binds to principal cells in the collecting duct that translocate aquaporins to the membrane, allowing water to leave the normally impermeable membrane and be reabsorbed into the body by the vasa recta, thus increasing the plasma volume of the body. There are two systems that create a hyperosmotic medulla and thus increase the body plasma volume:

A. Urea recycling: Urea is usually excreted as a waste product from the kidneys. However, when plasma blood volume is low and ADH is released the aquaporins that are opened are also permeable to urea. This allows urea to leave the collecting duct into the medulla creating a hyperosmotic solution that 'attracts' water. Urea can then re-enter the nephron and be excreted or recycled again depending on whether ADH is still present or not.

B. 'Single effect': It describes that the ascending thick limb of the loop of Henle is not permeable to water but is permeable to NaCl. This allows for a countercurrent exchange system whereby the medulla becomes increasingly concentrated, but at the same time setting

up an osmotic gradient for water to follow should the aquaporins of the collecting duct be opened by ADH.

5. Blood pressure regulation: Although the kidney cannot directly sense blood, long-term regulation of blood pressure predominantly depends upon the kidney. This primarily occurs through maintenance of the extracellular fluid compartment, the size of which depends on the plasma sodium concentration. Renin is the first in a series of important chemical messengers that make up the renin-angiotensin system. When renin levels are elevated, the concentrations of angiotensin II and aldosterone increase, leading to increased sodium chloride reabsorption, expansion of the extracellular fluid compartment, and an increase in blood pressure. Conversely, when renin levels are low, angiotensin II and aldosterone levels decrease, contracting the extracellular fluid compartment, and decreasing blood pressure.

6. Hormone secretion: The kidneys secrete a variety of hormones, including erythropoietin, calcitriol and the enzyme renin. Erythropoietin is released in response to hypoxia (low levels of oxygen at tissue level) in the renal circulation. It stimulates erythropoiesis (production of red blood cells) in the bone marrow. Calcitriol, the activated form of vitamin D, promotes intestinal absorption of calcium and the renal reabsorption of phosphate. Part of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, renin is an enzyme involved in the regulation of aldosterone levels.

RENAL FUNCTION: Renal function or Kidney function indicates how efficiently the kidneys filter blood. The two healthy kidneys have 100 percent of kidney function. Small or mild declines in kidney function-as much as 30 to 40% would rarely be noticeable. Kidney function is now calculated using a blood sample and a formula to find the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). The eGFR corresponds to the percent of kidney function available. For many people with reduced kidney function, a kidney disease is also present and will get worse. Serious health problems occur when people have less than 25 percent of their kidney function. When kidney function drops below 10 to 15 percent, a person needs some form of renal replacement therapy either blood-cleansing treatments called dialysis or a kidney transplant-to sustain life.¹

Calculations: The kidney function is estimated by calculating the following parameters

A. Filtration Fraction: The filtration fraction is the amount of plasma which is actually filtered through the kidney. This can be defined using the equation:

$$FF = GFR/RPF$$

FF is the filtration fraction, GFR is the glomerular filtration rate and RPF is the renal plasma flow. Normal human FF is 20%.

B. Renal Clearance: Renal clearance is the volume of plasma from which the substance is completely cleared from the blood per unit time.

$$C_x = (U_x)V/P_x$$

C_x is the clearance of X (normally in units of ml/min), U_x is the urine concentration of X, P_x is the plasma concentration of X and V is the urine flow rate.³

KIDNEY FAILURE:

Renal failure (also kidney failure or renal insufficiency) is a medical condition in which the kidneys fail to adequately filter waste products from the blood. The two main forms are acute kidney injury, which is often reversible with adequate treatment, and chronic kidney disease, which is often not reversible. In both cases, there is usually an underlying cause. Most kidney diseases attack the nephrons, causing them to lose their filtering capacity. Damage to the nephrons can happen quickly, often as the result of injury or poisoning. But most kidney diseases destroy the nephrons slowly and silently. Only after years or even decades will the damage become apparent. Most kidney diseases attack both kidneys simultaneously.

Renal failure is mainly determined by a decrease in glomerular filtration rate, the rate at which blood is filtered in the glomeruli of the kidney. This is detected by a decrease in or absence of urine production or determination of waste products (creatinine or urea) in the blood. Depending on the cause, hematuria (blood loss in the urine) and proteinuria (protein loss in the urine) may be noted. In renal failure, there may be problems with increased fluid in the body (leading to swelling), increased acid levels, raised levels of potassium, decreased levels of calcium, increased levels of phosphate, and in later stages anemia. Bone health may also be affected. Long-term kidney problems are associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease.

Classification: Renal failure can be categorized as following;

- A. Acute kidney injury
- B. Chronic kidney disease
- C. End stage renal disease
- D. Acute on Chronic renal failure

A. Acute kidney injury:

Acute kidney injury (AKI), previously called acute renal failure (ARF), is a rapidly progressive loss of renal function, generally characterized by oliguria (decreased urine production, quantified as less than 400 mL per day in adults, less than 0.5 mL/kg/h in children or less than 1 mL/kg/h in infants); and fluid and electrolyte imbalance. AKI can result from a variety of causes, generally classified as **prerenal, intrinsic, and postrenal**. The underlying cause must be identified and treated to arrest the progress, and dialysis may be necessary to bridge the time gap required for treating these fundamental causes.

B. Chronic kidney disease: *Chronic kidney disease (CKD) can also develop slowly and, initially, show few symptoms. CKD can be the long term consequence of irreversible acute disease or part of a disease progression. Most kidney problems, however, happen slowly. A person may have "silent" kidney disease for years. Gradual loss of kidney function is called chronic kidney disease (CKD) or chronic renal insufficiency. People with CKD may go on to develop permanent kidney failure. They also have a high risk of death from a stroke or heart attack.*

C. End-stage Renal Disease:

Total or nearly total and permanent kidney failure is called end-stage renal disease (ESRD).¹ESRD usually results from a progressive and irreversible loss of renal function and is defined by a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of less than 15 ml/min. People with ESRD must undergo dialysis or transplantation to stay alive. [14]

D. Acute-on-chronic renal failure:

Acute kidney injuries can be present on top of chronic kidney disease, a condition called acute-on-chronic renal failure (AoCRF). The acute part of AoCRF may be reversible, and the goal of treatment, as with AKI, is to return the patient to baseline renal function, typically measured by serum creatinine. Like AKI, AoCRF can be difficult to distinguish from chronic kidney disease if the patient has not been monitored by a physician and no baseline (i.e., past) blood work is available for comparison.

CAUSES FOR KIDNEY FAILURE:

Many factors that influence the speed of kidney failure are not completely understood. Researchers are still studying how protein in the diet and cholesterol levels in the blood affect kidney function. The two most common causes of kidney disease are diabetes and high blood pressure. People with a family history of any kind of kidney problem are also at risk for kidney disease.

1. Diabetic Kidney Disease:**2. High Blood Pressure****3. Glomerular Diseases:****4. Genetic predisposition:****5. Inherited and Congenital Kidney Disease****6. Other Causes of Kidney Disease:**

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Methodology**Study site:**

The study "A prospective observational study on Haemodialysis patients in a tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad" was carried out in the dialysis unit at Yashoda Hospital Malapet, Hyderabad; it is a 350 bedded multi-disciplinary tertiary care hospital.

1. Study duration:

The duration of the study was 6- months that was from December 2013 to may 2014.

2. Size of the study population:

50 haemodialysis cases were taken in this study.

3. Inclusion criteria:

Patients who are undergoing haemodialysis in the Dialysis Unit at yashoda hospital.

4. Exclusion criteria:

Haemodialysis patients who are not willing to participate in this study.

5. Patient enrollment:

Patients were enrolled in the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. .

RESULTS:

A prospective observational study was conducted for six months (dec-2013 to may-2014) in the Dialysis unit of yashoda hospital a Tertiary care hospital, hyderabad. A total of 50 Haemodialysis (HD) patients were selected for the study according to the inclusion criteria.

Evaluation of Data:

A total of 50 patients underwent haemodialysis, out of 3,100 IP (Inpatient) admissions during the study period. Out of 50 HD patients, 16 patients were new patients during the study period. The present study shows the Incidence for haemodialysis is 0.0.005 and the Prevalence for haemodialysis is 0.016.

I. Demographic Data of the HD patients:**1. Patient distribution based on gender:**

Out of 50 HD patients, 35 (70%) patients were male and 15 (30%) patients were female.

Table-2: Gender wise distribution

Sl. No.	Gender	No. of Patients	Percentage%
1	Male	35	70
2	Female	15	30

2.Patient distribution based on Age:

I categorized the patients according to their age groups. Out of 50 patients, majority of the 18 (36%) patients were found to be in the age group of 51-60 years, 19 (38%) patients were in the age group of 41-50 years, 6 (6%) patients were in the age group of 31-

40 years, 6 (12%) patients were in the age group of 61-70 years, 2 (4%) patients were in the age group of 21-30 years and finally 2 patients were in the age group of 71-80 years which is represented in the figure.1

3. Patient distribution based on Personal History & symptoms:

Table shows the patient distribution based on their personal history & symptoms. Among 50 patients, 20 (40%) patients were suffering from disturbed sleep,

5(10%) patients were having altered bowel & bladder habits and 25(50%) patients were having altered appetite. Out of 50 patients, 10 (20%) patients were smokers and 18 (36%) patients were alcoholics and 22(44%) patients are non smokers and non alcoholics.

Table-3: Patient distribution based on Personal History & symptoms:

Sl. No.	Personal History & Symptoms	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)	
1	Personal History	Smokers	10	20
		Alcoholics	18	36
		Non alcoholics and non smokers	22	44
	Disturbed sleep	25	50	
2	Symptoms	Altered appetite	20	40
		Altered bowel and bladder	5	10

4. Patient distribution basing on current and previous Employment Status:

Table-6.4-A& Figure-6.4-A shows the patient distribution based on their both previous and current employment status. Out of 50 HD patients, previously the patients were working for full time, Retired due to disabilities & unemployed were 24 (48%), 0 (0%) and 26 (52%) patients respectively where-as currently only 3 (6%) patients are working for full time, 21 (42%) patients Retired due to disabilities and 26 (52%) patients are unemployed.

Table -4: Patient distribution based on Previous and Current Employment status

Sl. No.	Prior status	No. of patients (%)	Current status	No. of patients (%)
1	Full time	24 (48)	Full time	3 (6)
2	Retired due to disabilities	0 (0)	Retired due to disabilities	21 (42)
3	Unemployed	26 (52)	Unemployed	26 (52)

Patient distribution based on Past Medical History:

Out of 50 HD patients, 19(38%) patients (Male patients-16& Female patients-3) had HTN alone, 16 (32%) patients (Male patients-11& Female patients-5) had both HTN & DM, 13 (26%) patients (Male patients-9& Female patients-4) had DM alone and 2 (4%) patients (Male patients-1& Female patients-1) had hypothyroidism disease.

5. Patient distribution based on Duration of Dialysis

Out of 50 HD patients, 10 (20%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for >3 years, 7(14%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for 2-3 years, 10 (20%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for the duration of 1-2 years,7(14%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for the duration of 6 months to1 years, whereas 16 (32%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis < 6 months period.

Patient distribution based on Duration of Dialysis figure 2

6. Risk Factors

1. Patient distribution based on Non-Modifiable risk factors

Out of 50 HD patients, the non-modifiable risk factors HTN alone and DM alone were seen in 19 (38%) patients (Male patients-16 & Female patients-3) and 13 (26%) patients (Male patients-9& Female patient-4), 16(32%) patients were having HTN & DM (Male patients-11 & Female patients-5), 2(4%) patients were having hypothyroidism (Male

2. Patient distribution based on Modifiable risk factors

Out of 50 patients, 18 (36%) patient were having alcohol habit, 10 (20%) patients were having smoking habit and 22 (44%) patients were having drug induced renal failure.

patients-1 & Female patients-1) . Dialysis – Complications

Patient distribution based on Intra Dialysis Complications

Out of 50 HD patients, 18 (36%) patients suffered from weakness, 4 (8%) patients suffered from headache, 5 (10%) patients suffered from fever & chills, 8 (16%) patients suffered from nausea &

vomiting, 6 (12%) patients suffered from itching, 2 (4%) patients suffered from SOB and same as from

hypotension and 1 (2%) patient suffered from cramps. figure 3

2. Patient distribution based on long term Dialysis Complications Table-5 shows the patient distribution based on the long term dialysis complications. Out of 50 HD patients, mostly HCV infections was observed

in 30 (60%) patients and depression was observed in 16 (32%) patients where-as 34 (68%) patients had malnutrition.

Patient distribution based on long term Dialysis Complications Table 5

Sl	Complications	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
1	HCV Infection	30	60
2	Disequilibrium syndrome	0	0
3	Malnutrition	34	68
4	Cardiac arrhythmias	0	0
5	Hemorrhage	0	0
6	GI effects	2	4
7	Psychiatric Illness (Depression)	16	32
8	Nil	0	0

DISCUSSION:

Kidney diseases are highly prevalent globally. They have become a major public health problem and associated with considerable co-morbidity and mortality. Maintenance dialysis therapy is the commonest mode of Renal Replacement Therapy (RRT) and demand for this service is increasingly progressively worldwide. Over one million people worldwide are alive on dialysis. In UK, AKI requiring dialysis is 200ppm and in USA by 2010, >6 laces patients were on RRT (Dialysis). In India, it is estimated that about 1 lake persons suffer from ESRD each year.

The risk factors for prevalence and incidence of renal failure are majorly hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Though haemodialysis is a better method of RRT,

there are some complications associated with haemodialysis.

In my study, I had recruited 50 haemodialysis patients, from the results we obtained in our study, the average hospital bed strength statistics for a period of 6 months is 3,100 and the prevalence for HD was estimated at 0.016. The incidence of renal failure was estimated at 0.005. There is a high prevalence and incidence of renal failure and this was supported by the study “**Epidemiology of haemodialysis patients in Aleppo city**”, conducted by **Ghamez Moukeh et al.**

Out of 50 HD patients, 35 (70%) patients accounted as male and 15 (30%) were female. So male are more prone to renal failure then female so they undergoing haemodialysis. This is more or less concordant to a study conducted by **Wiam AA et al.** on

“Epidemiology and etiology do dialysis treated end stage kidney disease in Libya”

In my study, most of the patients (50%) had disturbed sleep and this was supported by the study “**A study on insomnia in chronic renal patients on dialysis in Saudi-Arabia**” conducted by **Hamdan H Al-Jahdali et al.** Out Of 50 HD patients 10 (20%) patients were smokers and 18 (36%) patients were alcoholics and 22(44%) patients don't have smoking and alcoholic habit.

Out of 50 HD patients, 24 (48%) patients were working for full time previously where as currently only 3 (6%) patients continue the same, and 21(42%) patients are retired due to disabilities and 26 (52%) patients remained unemployed. This was supported by the study “**Clinical epidemiology of long bone fractures in patients receiving Haemodialysis**” conducted by **Kaneko TM et al.**

In my study I was observed 49 (98%) patients were suffering from CKD, and 1 (2%) patients were suffering from AKI. Most of the HD patients are treated with the drugs like Amlodipine, Atenolol, Losartan, Clonidine, prazosin, nifedipine, metoprolol, clopidrigyle, thyroxine etc.

Out of 50 HD patients, 10 (20%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for >3 years, 10 (20%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis for the duration of 1-2 years where as 16 (32%) patients were undergoing haemodialysis<6 months period.

My study shows, most of the patients have the non-modifiable risk factor HTN alone 19(38%) and 13(26%) patients have DM alone and HTN & DM, 2(4%) patients have hypothyroidism. I also observed that modifiable risk factors that is 18 (36%) alcoholics patients, 10 (20%) smoking and 22(44%) drug induced This was supported by the study “**Epidemiology of haemodialysis patients in Aleppo city**”, conducted by **Ghamez Moukeh et al.** Most of the patients suffered from the intra dialysis complications such as weakness (36%) and nausea and vomiting (16%) where-as the long term dialysis complications like HCV Infection (60%), malnutrition (68%), psychiatric illness (34%), and GI effects (4%).

CONCLUSION:

In HYDERABAD region, there is a relatively high prevalence and incidence of renal failure. Hypertension and Diabetes mellitus are the leading causes for the kidney diseases. Weakness, nausea and vomiting are the prominent intra dialysis

complications. HCV infections and psychiatric illness are the long term dialysis complications. So maintenance of hygienic conditions during dialysis and patients counseling is needed.

Awareness and counseling of haemodialysis patients on the disease, medication, diet along with the life style modifications is necessary for the patients to control their risk factors, intra and long term complications.

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